

Machine Learning Application to the Identification of Sheet Metal Constitutive Model Parameters

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Abstract

In this work, the application of machine learning algorithms to the identification of constitutive model parameters is explored. Multiple machine learning algorithms are tested, considering two different datasets, one including uniaxial tensile test results, and the other including biaxial tensile test results. Of the algorithms tested, Gaussian Processes achieved the best predictive performances. Afterwards, the influence of dataset size is explored, considering both the number of materials included in the dataset, and the number of input parameters. For the latter, a feature importance methodology, namely SHAP (Shapley Additive Explanations) analysis, is applied to identify the most relevant input parameters in the datasets. The performance of the models trained with the inputs identified by the SHAP analysis is competitive for one of the datasets, which shows the potential of this type of analysis to create more efficient parameter identification methodologies.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Constitutive Modelling, Parameter Identification, Data-driven Learning, Sheet Metal Forming

1 - Introduction

Sheet metal forming is a manufacturing process of significant relevance in the automotive and aerospace industries, due to its capacity to produce a high volume of components at a relatively low cost [1]. In order to answer the demands of these extremely competitive industries, researchers are constantly looking for ways to increase the efficiency of this manufacturing process. In this context, one of the priorities was replacing the trial-and-error approach to the design process, due to the significant costs in terms of time and scrap rate [2]. Since these forming processes are highly non-linear, in regard to the material properties, boundary conditions and geometry, the creation of analytical solutions is unfeasible, which led researchers to look for alternatives, such as the finite element analysis (FEA). For the application of FEA simulations to be possible, the mechanical behaviour of the materials must be accurately represented, which is usually done through constitutive models [3].

As new metallic alloys are developed, to address the demands of the industry, more flexible constitutive models, with a larger number of parameters, are required, which in turn makes the identification of those parameters more complex. In order to optimize the constitutive model parameter identification process, researchers are seeking new identification strategies, with a recent focus on the application of Machine Learning (ML) techniques. For example, Cruz et al. [4] identified the Swift hardening law parameters, using an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) trained with data from the force displacement curves obtained for the punch during three point bending tests. Morand et al. [5] used a mixture of experts, in the form of an ensemble model comprised of multiple neural networks, to identify hardening parameters for an identification problem with non-unique solutions. Basically, the hardening law chosen can have multiple sets of parameters representing the same mechanical behaviour, and the authors defend that for these situations, an ensemble model should be used, since a single model, such as an ANN, has a tendency to average the potential parameter sets, leading to low predictive performance. Guo et al. [6] developed a deep learning model to identify constitutive parameters, based on the combination of a convolutional neural network, used to filter noise in the input data, with a long-short term memory neural network. This model was used to identify the elastic parameters (Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio) and three parameters of an exponential hardening law. The proposed model was tested using noisy data, and proved to be sufficiently noise resistant, maintaining low identification errors. Further validation was performed by comparing the performance of the proposed model with that of a Finite Element Model Updating (FEMU) method, based on data containing experimental results of an

aluminium alloy uniaxial tensile test. Both methods obtained similar identifications, but the authors emphasised the significant difference in efficiency between the two methods. The ML method takes a long time to train, resulting in a significantly longer time to obtain the first identification, when compared to the time it takes the FEMU method to make a single identification. However, subsequent identifications by the ML method are almost instantaneous, while the FEMU method must repeat the entire optimization process for each individual material, making the ML method much more efficient for subsequent identifications, after training. Another advantage of the ML method is the fact that, once the training process is finished, the work necessary for new identifications can be done by non-specialized operators.

The various applications of ML to constitutive model parameter identification found in the literature are mainly focused on the use of neural network algorithms, neglecting the potential of the other ML algorithms available [7, 8]. The selection of this algorithm is usually based on subjective criteria, and to the authors' knowledge, no in-depth study has been conducted that compared the application of the many ML algorithms available to the identification of constitutive model parameters. Also, a review of the current state of the art shows that most applications are based on data obtained from simple tests, such as uniaxial tensile tests and shear tests [9]. The use of more complex, non-homogeneous mechanical tests, which allow for the characterization of more complex constitutive models, such as the biaxial tensile test with a cruciform specimen, is not thoroughly explored.

In order to address these limitations, the main goal of the present work is to develop a methodology for the identification of constitutive model parameters based on the application of ML, that explores the potential of various ML algorithms and is based on data obtained from multiple mechanical tests, including the biaxial tensile test with a cruciform specimen. To reach this objective, several ML algorithms including Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), Gaussian Process Regression (GPR), Support Vector Regression (SVR) and Random Forest (RF) were considered. These algorithms were applied to the identification of the Swift hardening law and Hill'48 yield criterion parameters, based on data obtain from the numerical simulation of two types of mechanical tests: uniaxial tensile tests, and biaxial tensile tests with a cruciform sample. Then, the influence of dataset size in the predictive performance of the algorithms was evaluated, and a SHAP analysis was performed in order to better understand which data inputs were the most influential in the parameter's identification.

2 – Machine Learning

Machine learning (ML) is a research field that aims to develop systems that can improve themselves without explicit programming [10]. ML algorithms are particularly useful for solving complex problems that would normally require building first-principle models and implementing problem-specific algorithms, which can be prohibitively expensive and time-consuming. These algorithms can be categorized based on the configuration of data they require. These categories are supervised learning algorithms [11], unsupervised learning algorithms [12] and reinforcement learning algorithms [13].

The algorithms used in this work are supervised algorithms. These algorithms learn to generalize a problem from labelled data, which means that the dataset used contains both the inputs and outputs of the problem. This learning process is generally referred to as "training" and consists of mapping the relationships between the input variables and the output variables that are present in the training dataset provided to the algorithm. Based on these relationships, a model's internal parameters are calibrated, allowing it to predict outputs for new inputs. The following sections present the ML algorithms considered for this work. These algorithms have significantly different formulations, but all are suitable for regression problems. Since the problem of constitutive model parameter identification is a regression problem, all these algorithms are suitable, and in the current work the performance of each algorithm will be evaluated, in order to identify which algorithm is most appropriate for this type of application.

2.1 - Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP)

The Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) is a feed forward neural network applicable to both classification and regression problems, composed of multiple layers of nodes (neurons) [14]. Each node of a given layer connects to the neurons of the next layer, passing information, but never connects with other nodes of the same layer. The first layer of an MLP is called the input layer and contains as many nodes as there are input features in the dataset. It is followed by any number of layers called hidden layers. The number of hidden layers, as well as the number of nodes in each hidden layer are defined before the training process. In the last layer, called output layer, predictions are made based on the information received from the previous layer. This algorithm is applicable to multi-output problems natively, with the number of nodes in the output layer being equal to the number of output variables of the problem. The output of a single node from a hidden layer is given by:

$$z_i = \phi(\sum_j w_{ij}z'_j + d_i), \quad (1)$$

where z_i is the output of node i from the current layer, z'_j is the output of node j from the previous layer, w_{ij} is the weight associated with z'_j , d_i is a bias term and \emptyset is a non-linear activation function. The training of this type of model is based on the so-called backpropagation algorithm [15]. This consists in assessing whether each weight value should be increased or decreased to increase performance, then changing all the weights in the network accordingly by a small increment. This is an iterative process that continues until a minimum prediction error estimate is achieved.

2.2 - Gaussian Process Regression (GPR)

A Gaussian Process is a collection of random variables that follows a Gaussian distribution and are fully defined by a mean function and a covariance function [16]. In general, the covariance function is enough to fully define the Gaussian Process, as the mean function is assumed to be zero [17]. The GPR model can be represented by:

$$\mathbf{y}(\mathbf{x}) = f(\mathbf{x}) + \epsilon, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{y}(\mathbf{x})$ is an observed output, $f(\mathbf{x})$ is the corresponding Gaussian Process variable and ϵ represents a zero mean Gaussian white noise. Assuming that $\mathbf{y}(\mathbf{x}^t)$ is the target vector of outputs present in the dataset, and $\mathbf{y}(\mathbf{x}^p)$ is the vector of outputs to be predicted, the joint normal probability distribution is given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y}(\mathbf{x}^t) \\ \mathbf{y}(\mathbf{x}^p) \end{bmatrix} \sim N \left(0, \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}) + \sigma_\epsilon^2 \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}_*) \\ \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}_*, \mathbf{X}) & \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}_*, \mathbf{X}_*) \end{bmatrix} \right), \quad (3)$$

where σ_ϵ^2 represents the noise variance, \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix and each \mathbf{K} is a covariance matrix evaluated for all considered points, with \mathbf{X} representing the training data from the dataset, and \mathbf{X}_* the unseen data for which the model will make predictions. Finally, the predictions are given by the following equations:

$$\bar{\mathbf{f}}_* = \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}_*, \mathbf{X}) [\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}) + \sigma_\epsilon^2 \mathbf{I}]^{-1} \mathbf{y}(\mathbf{x}^t), \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{cov}(\mathbf{f}_*) = \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}_*, \mathbf{X}_*) - \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}_*, \mathbf{X}) [\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}) + \sigma_\epsilon^2 \mathbf{I}]^{-1} \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}_*), \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{f}}_*$ is the vector of predictions (mean), and $\mathbf{cov}(\mathbf{f}_*)$ represents the covariance of model outputs, which acts as a measure of prediction uncertainty. This covariance measurement can be useful, both to evaluate the quality of GPR model predictions, and to support online active learning. However, since it is a specific metric of this algorithm, it will not be considered in this work, in favour of metrics that can be applied to models trained by various algorithms, so the performances are easily comparable.

2.3 - Support Vector Regression (SVR)

The support vector regression (SVR) algorithm fits a function to the available data, while remaining as flat as possible. To achieve this, an error value γ is determined, under which errors are accepted without penalty [18]. In practice, this means finding a function that can encompass the most training data points in the area around it, with a distance of γ or less. Since this restriction can be unfeasible, soft margins can be defined, in the form of slack variables ξ_i and ξ_i^* , which give the resulting model more flexibility. Points at a distance between these variables and γ still affect the shape of the function, but under a penalty. When considering a linear problem, the problem is described by:

$$\begin{cases} \min \left(\frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{w}\|^2 + V \sum_i (\xi_i + \xi_i^*) \right) \\ \text{with:} \\ y_i - wx_i - \beta_0 \leq \gamma + \xi_i \\ wx_i + \beta_0 - y_i \leq \gamma + \xi_i^* \end{cases}, \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{w} is the normal weight vector to the surface of the function that is being approximated and V is a constant representing the trade-off between tolerance for deviations above γ and the flatness of the function. In case of problem non-linearity, this algorithm can be generalized by introducing a kernel trick [19]. A kernel is a similarity function between the inputs of the training data and inputs for which the model will make predictions. With a kernel trick, a linear model can learn non-linear functions without specific mapping, by transforming the data into a higher dimensional space.

2.4 - Random Forest (RF)

A Random Forest (RF) is an ensemble of decision trees, each trained with a randomly generated sample from the training data [20]. A decision tree is a model based on the continuous splitting of the available training data, based on simple rules. The optimization of these splitting rules is based on the minimization of an error metric in the resulting final nodes [21]. The most common error metric used on this case is the MSE (mean squared error). The splitting process is repeated until each of the resulting final nodes has an MSE under a previously defined threshold, or until all final nodes have a number of training points under a specified value. The predictions from each node correspond to the average of the output values from the training points in the node. The predictions made by the random forest model correspond to the average value of the predictions made by each decision tree.

3 – Numerical Models and Dataset Generation

This section presents the numerical models of the mechanical tests, the materials considered, and the process of generating the datasets necessary to the application of the ML algorithms.

3.1 – Numerical Models

In this work two different mechanical tests are considered: uniaxial tensile tests and biaxial tensile tests with a cruciform sample. While the results from the uniaxial tensile tests could be obtained analytically, the use of numerical simulations was chosen, so that the results of both mechanical tests are obtained under the same conditions.

The finite element mesh of the uniaxial tensile test sample, represented in Figure 1, contains 5160 eight-node hexahedral solid elements. This sample has outer dimensions of 90 mm length and 20 mm width, and the inner rectangular area has a length of 65 mm and a width of 10 mm. The geometry of the biaxial cruciform tensile test sample is represented in Figure 2 a), which was proposed in [22], and the respective finite element mesh is represented in Figure 2 b). This mesh contains 6680 eight-node hexahedral solid elements, and only represents one eighth of the sample, due to material and geometrical symmetries. The total length of each arm is 73.6 mm. For both mechanical tests, the initial sample thickness is 0.5 mm.

Fig.1 Finite element mesh of the uniaxial tensile test.

Fig.2 a) Geometry of biaxial tensile test with a cruciform sample [22], b) Finite element mesh of the biaxial tensile test.

The numerical simulations were carried out with the in-house finite element code DD3IMP, developed and optimized for the simulation of metal forming processes [23–25]. For this work, the constitutive model hypoelastic formulation assumes that the incremental total strain tensor can be additively split into elastic and plastic components. An isotropic elastic behaviour was assumed, described by the generalized Hooke's law, while the plastic behaviour is considered anisotropic, described by the orthotropic Hill'48 yield criterion [26] and the Swift hardening law [27].

The Hill'48 yield criterion is given by the following equation:

$$F(\sigma_{yy} - \sigma_{zz})^2 + G(\sigma_{zz} - \sigma_{xx})^2 + H(\sigma_{xx} - \sigma_{yy})^2 + 2L\tau_{yz}^2 + 2M\tau_{xz}^2 + 2N\tau_{xy}^2 = Y^2, \quad (7)$$

where σ_{xx} , σ_{yy} , σ_{zz} , τ_{xy} , τ_{yz} and τ_{xz} are the components of the Cauchy stress tensor defined in the orthotropic coordinate system of the material, O_{xyz} ; F , G , H , L , M and N are the anisotropy parameters and Y represents the yield stress and its evolution during deformation. The condition $G + H = 1$ is assumed and so Y evolution is comparable to the uniaxial tensile curve along the rolling direction of the sheet. The parameters L and M are assumed equal to 1.5, as in isotropy (von Mises). The F , G , H and N parameters are related to the Lankford coefficients, also known as anisotropy coefficients, r_0 , r_{45} , and r_{90} , as follows:

$$F = \frac{r_0}{r_{90}(r_0 + 1)}, G = \frac{1}{r_0 + 1}, H = \frac{r_0}{r_0 + 1}, N = \frac{1}{2} \frac{(r_0 + r_{90})(2r_{45} + 1)}{r_{90}(r_0 + 1)}. \quad (8)$$

The Swift hardening law is given by the following equation:

$$Y = C (\varepsilon_0 + \bar{\varepsilon}^p)^n. \quad (9)$$

where $\bar{\varepsilon}^p$ is the equivalent plastic strain and C , ε_0 and n are material parameters. The initial yield stress, Y_0 , is given by:

$$Y_0 = C \varepsilon_0^n \quad (10)$$

3.2 – Dataset Generation

Two different datasets were generated for this work. The first dataset, hereby referred to as dataset A, contains as input data the results of the uniaxial tensile tests, considering three different directions in relation to the rolling direction (0° , 45° and 90°). For these tests, the values of force and the Green Lagrange strain tensor components ε_{xx} , ε_{yy} and ε_{xy} in specific nodes of the finite element mesh were extracted. These results occurred in displacement increments of 0.5 mm, up to a total displacement of 6 mm. The maximum value of force achieved during the test was also included. Due to the uniformity of the strains along the sample, the strains were extracted from only 22 nodes, as represented in Figure 1.

The second dataset, hereby referred to as dataset B, contains the results of the biaxial tensile tests as input data. The input data includes the forces measured along both the 0_x and 0_y axis, and Green Lagrange strain tensor components ε_{xx} , ε_{yy} , and ε_{xy} . These measurements occurred in displacement increments of 0.2 mm, up to a total displacement of 2 mm, considering that the displacement rate along both axis is the same. The strains were extracted from a total of 82 nodes, shown in Figure 2 b). These nodes are uniformly distributed along the specimen, except at the notch, where a higher concentration of nodes was used to obtain more information about the shear strain components. Figure 3 shows the ε_{xx} , ε_{yy} , and ε_{xy} distributions along the cruciform specimen, obtained from one of the materials present in dataset B.

Fig.3 Strain fields obtained for a biaxial tensile test for a total displacement of 2mm a) ϵ_{xx} , b) ϵ_{yy} ,
c) ϵ_{xy} .

To be able to accurately identify the material parameters independently of the elastic behaviour, the value of the Young's Modulus (E) is also considered as input, in both datasets. In total, dataset A contains 2416 different input features, ($[3 \text{ strain components} \times 22 \text{ nodes} + \text{force}] \times 12 \text{ displacement increments} + \text{max force}$) $\times 3$ tensile tests + E ; and dataset B contains 2481 different input features, $(3 \text{ strain components} \times 82 \text{ nodes} + 2 \text{ forces}) \times 10 \text{ displacement increments} + E$.

The output data for both datasets consists of the constitutive parameters to be identified, namely the Y_0 , C and n parameters of the Swift hardening law and the F , G and N parameters of the Hill'48 yield criterion. In short, dataset A contains 2416 input features and 6 output features, while dataset B contains 2481 input features and 6 output features.

The various materials used in this work were generated following the limits presented in Table 1. The Hill'48 parameters correspond to a variability of r values between 0.6 and 5.7. These limits were selected to include various steel, aluminium, and titanium grades, which are typically used in sheet metal forming processes. In order to represent the

possible influence of the elastic behaviour of these types of materials in the mechanical test results used as inputs, three different values of E were considered: 70, 140 and 210 GPa. In all cases, the Poisson's ratio considered is 0.3.

Table 1 - Limits of each parameter used to generate the material constitutive model parameter sets.

	F	G	N	ϵ_0	n	$Y_0[MPa]$
Lower Limit	0.06	0.25	0.45	0.002	0.12	150
Upper Limit	1.24	0.625	6.63	0.03	0.25	1200

Each dataset can be divided into a training set, used by the algorithms during the training process, and a testing set, for which predictions/identifications will be made by the trained models. For the training set, a total of 4096 different sets of material constitutive parameters were generated by a Sobol sequence [28], which provides a more uniform parameter distribution when compared to a purely random distribution. The testing set contains 500 different materials, obtained from Latin Hypercube distribution [29]. After the plastic behaviour parameters were generated, each material was assigned a value of E , so that the three possible values presented previously are distributed uniformly.

4 – Hyperparameter calibration

The predictive models were constructed using the ML algorithms presented previously, with the publicly available library Scikit-learn [30]: Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), Gaussian Process Regression (GPR), Support Vector Regression (SVR) and Random Forest (RF).

Data scaling was performed for both datasets, so that each constitutive parameter varies between 0 and 1. Afterwards, an optimization of the ML algorithm hyperparameters was performed. In this work, the hyperparameter optimization step consists of a trial-and-error process, in which the training set is randomly split into two sets, a temporary training set containing 70% of the data, and a validation set containing the remaining 30% of the data. This split is repeated 30 times, and for each split, a model is trained with the temporary training set, predictions are obtained for the validation set, and the predictive performance is evaluated. Then, the hyperparameters used to train the models are changed and the process is repeated. The set of hyperparameters that led to the best performance during this step is then used to train the final models. The selected hyperparameters for dataset A are shown in Table 2 while Table 3 presents the hyperparameters selected for dataset B.

Table 2 – Hyperparameters used for model training using dataset A.

MLP	Number of hidden layers	Nodes per layer	\emptyset	Solver
	2	100/100	tanh	LBFGS ¹
GPR	Kernel function			
	RBF ²			
SVR	Kernel function	degree	V	γ
	Polynomial	5	0.0001	0.0005
RF	Number of estimators	Splitting criterion	Min samples leaf	
	1000	MSE ³	1	

1 – Limited-memory BFGS [31]; 2 – Radial Basis Function; 3 – Mean square error.

Table 3 - Hyperparameters used for model training using dataset B.

MLP	Number of hidden layers	Nodes per layer	\emptyset	Solver
	3	100/100/20	tanh	LBFGS ¹
GPR	Kernel function			
	RBF ²			
SVR	Kernel function	degree	V	γ
	Polynomial	4	0.000001	0.0001
RF	Number of estimators	Splitting criterion	Min samples leaf	
	1000	MSE ³	1	

1 – Limited-memory BFGS [31]; 2 – Radial Basis Function; 3 – Mean square error.

5 – Performance evaluation

The predictive performance evaluation is based on performance metrics. In this work, three metrics were considered. The first metric is the root mean square relative error (RMSRE), which is given by:

$$\text{RMSRE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{j} \sum_{i=1}^j \left(\frac{y_i - y_i^*}{y_i} \right)^2}, \quad (11)$$

where y and y^* are the real and predicted values for the output variables, respectively, and j is the test set size. This is the only metric considered during the hyperparameter optimization step. The second metric is the maximum absolute error (MAE), which is given by:

$$\text{MAE} = \max_i |y_i - y_i^*|, \quad (12)$$

In this work, this metric will be considered as a complement to the RMSRE. While the RMSRE is the main indicator of the overall predictive performance of the models, the MAE is an indicator of the amplitude of error that can be expected from future predictions. This helps understand how well the models can make predictions for possible outliers in the testing sets. The final metric is the R-squared value, calculated as:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^j (y_i - y_i^*)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^j (y_i - \bar{y})^2}, \quad (13)$$

where \bar{y} is the average of the real values of the output variables. This metric expresses the extent to which the variance of the output variables is explained by the independent variables in the model. As such, it indicates how likely the model is to make good predictions for unseen data.

6 – Initial Results

In order to evaluate the predictive performance of the ML algorithms under study, models were trained with the full training sets. As previously stated, these training sets contain a total of 4096 materials. Then, these models were used to make predictions for the testing sets, and the performance metrics were calculated. These metrics are presented in Table 4, for dataset A, and Table 5, for dataset B. The best performances are highlighted.

Table 4 – Performance metrics achieved for dataset A, when training the models with the full training set.

	RMSRE (%)				R ²				MAE			
	MLP	GPR	SVR	RF	MLP	GPR	SVR	RF	MLP	GPR	SVR	RF
Y_0	3.3818	0.2549	1.4699	14.675	0.995	0.9999	0.9989	0.9624	148.463	22.56	79.058	273.58
C	2.4815	0.1528	0.2664	14.557	0.9985	0.9984	0.9999	0.9617	231.913	22.68	31.593	1813.78
n	1.4794	0.9215	1.8417	6.223	0.9946	0.9998	0.9923	0.9076	0.0161	0.0093	0.0187	0.0371
F	4.8179	0.1308	1.812	23.165	0.9969	0.9999	0.9982	0.9276	0.056	0.0074	0.098	0.2477
G	0.9249	0.0444	0.1444	4.517	0.9989	0.9999	0.9999	0.9757	0.0217	0.0017	0.0038	0.0611
N	2.7312	0.0735	0.7539	20.4628	0.9975	0.9999	0.9996	0.893	0.2465	0.0097	0.2528	1.3496

Table 5 – Performance metrics achieved for dataset B, when training the models with the full training set.

	RMSRE (%)				R ²				MAE			
	MLP	GPR	SVR	RF	MLP	GPR	SVR	RF	MLP	GPR	SVR	RF
Y_0	4.2054	0.4611	1.802	14.3594	0.9944	0.9999	0.9986	0.9641	163.602	29.932	80.753	281.78
C	4.8006	0.183	1.6273	14.1988	0.9943	0.9998	0.9991	0.9588	786.523	144.08	179.54	1560.71
n	2.5742	2.181	3.2058	8.8767	0.9834	0.9915	0.9762	0.8135	0.0248	0.0374	0.0466	0.0562
F	8.1009	0.2422	2.9036	21.3206	0.9936	0.9999	0.9984	0.9289	0.0789	0.0197	0.0926	0.2559
G	1.2561	0.0688	0.4231	4.4957	0.9979	0.9999	0.9997	0.9747	0.0183	0.0065	0.0132	0.055
N	4.3589	0.1413	0.8985	15.233	0.9939	0.9999	0.9995	0.9267	0.3714	0.0387	0.2121	1.3131

It is clear that the best predictive performances were consistently achieved by the GPR models, considering both datasets. The performances achieved by these models highlight the capabilities of the algorithm, considering the high non-linearity inherent to the problem of constitutive model parameter identification. The SVR models, while always behind the GPR models in terms of performance, still managed overall good predictions, and can be considered competitive alternatives. The MLP models perform noticeably worse than previously mentioned models, except for the prediction of the n parameter of the Swift hardening law, where the MLP models perform better than the SVR

models, for both datasets. Finally, the RF models perform significantly worse than the remaining models in all cases. There is a direct correlation between the RMSRE and MAE values achieved by the various models. The models that achieved the lowest values of RMSRE also achieved the lowest values of MAE, which shows that the models were capable of learning the problem consistently, without significant overfitting.

When comparing the performances obtained between the two datasets, the models trained with dataset A achieved generally better performances than the models trained with dataset B. For example, for the GPR algorithm, the average RMSRE values achieved are 0.26% for dataset A and 0.55% for dataset B. In regard to the Swift hardening law parameters, the best results were obtained with dataset A, because the uniaxial tensile tests reach higher strain values than the biaxial tensile tests. As such, the hardening evolution is better defined by the information contained in the first dataset. As for the Hill'48 yield criterion parameters, the better performances obtained using dataset A are partially explained by the choice of mechanical tests. As shown previously in equation 8, these parameters can be fully identified by the three uniaxial tensile tests.

7 – Dataset Reduction

The predictive performance of the ML models depends on the quantity and quality of the data used to train them [32]. As such, in order to evaluate the impact of the number of materials included in the training set, on the performance of the ML models, new training sets were generated, by continuously reducing the number of materials by half. The new training sets contain 2056, 1028, 512, 254 and 128 materials. These training sets were used by the MLP, GPR and SVR, algorithms to train new models, and the predictive performance achieved with these new models was evaluated with the same testing sets used in the previous examples. The RF algorithm was not included in this analysis, since its performances were significantly worse than those achieved by the remaining algorithms when applied to the original training sets. The RMSRE values achieved by the models, when trained with the various training set sizes, are represented in Figure 4.

Fig.4 RMSRE values achieved by the models, for the various training set sizes and ML algorithms: a) MLP for dataset A, b) MLP for dataset B, c) GPR for dataset A, d) GPR for dataset B, e) SVR for dataset A, f) SVR for dataset B.

In general, the reduction of training set size leads to an increase in the RMSRE values achieved by the models. This is particularly noticeable for the models trained with the GPR and SVR algorithms, which maintain relatively stable values of RMSRE when trained

using training sets down to 1024 materials, and then an exponential increase of RMSRE for the smaller training sets. On the other hand, the models trained with the MLP algorithm don't show such a clear trend. The increase in RMSRE with the decrease in training set size is not substantial, and in some cases a smaller training set leads to better predictive performance. As such, the GPR and SVR algorithms seem to benefit significantly more from the increase in training set size than the MLP algorithm.

Regarding the relative performance of the models, the models trained with the GPR algorithm maintain the best average performances comparatively to the other algorithms, for training set sizes of 512 materials and above. However, for the smallest training set of 128 materials, both the SVM and MLP models achieve better performances than the GPR model. This shows that the performance of the GPR models is more affected by the amount of information available during the training process.

8 – Feature Importance

Another aspect of dataset size to consider is the number of input parameters included. Generally, the inclusion of more input data is beneficial to the predictive performance of the ML models. However, the inclusion of more input parameters will inevitably lead to longer training times. By applying a feature selection methodology, it is possible to remove unnecessary features from the dataset, without significant loss of information, which has the benefit of reducing the amount of data that needs to be gathered before making new predictions.

The feature importance evaluation methodology used in this work consists of the application of Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) [33]. SHAP analysis is derived from the calculation of classic Shapley Values [34]. The Shapley value of an input feature i (Φ_i) is given by the following equation:

$$\Phi_i = \sum_{S \subseteq F \setminus \{i\}} \frac{|S|! (|F| - |S| - 1)!}{|F|!} [f_{S \cup \{i\}}(x_{S \cup \{i\}}) - f_S(x_S)], \quad (14)$$

where F is the set of all input features, S is a subset of F that does not include feature i , f_S is a model trained with feature set S , $f_{S \cup \{i\}}$ is a model trained with the same feature set, including feature i , x_S represents the values of the features in S and $x_{S \cup \{i\}}$ represents the values of the features in S and feature i . The calculation of Shapley values is computationally expensive. As such, SHAP analysis estimates these values in a more efficient way. In this work, Kernel SHAP [34] was used to obtain the SHAP values, which estimates them through a linear regression,

without the need to calculate all the possible permutations of input features [34]. This approximation method is applicable to all ML models.

SHAP values represent the influence that the presence of the input parameter has on the value of the prediction for each model output and are calculated for each instance in the dataset. An input parameter with high absolute SHAP values for a specific output, is a parameter that influences the model predictions for that output, while an input parameter with SHAP values near zero for all outputs could be taken out of the dataset, without significantly affecting the model predictive capabilities.

This analysis is also a possible solution for another typical ML issue, the problem of interpretability. With some notable exceptions, such as Decision Tree models, ML models are considered black box models, since it is nearly impossible to understand the relations between inputs and outputs, that lead to predictions. By establishing which input features are the most influential in predicting each output, SHAP analysis helps understand the relationships that were established by the model during training, and as such helps to explain the predictions obtained. However, it is important to note that these relations are only relevant for the model in question. This means that the input parameters with the highest SHAP values are the ones that influence the model predictions the most, but does not guarantee that they are also, in general, the parameters most correlated with the outputs.

SHAP analysis was applied to the GPR models, trained with 1024 materials, considering both datasets included in this work. These models were chosen since the GPR models achieved the best predictive performances overall, and at 1024 training materials, there is still a good compromise between performance and training set size. In this analysis, the 50 most influential input parameters in each model were identified. The results from this analysis are represented in Figures 5 and 6, for dataset A and B, respectively. These figures present the sums of the average SHAP values obtained for the 50 most influential parameters. In Figure 5, the labels indicate the moment in the tensile test, in terms of displacement value, when the force or strain is obtained, as well as which of the three tests the results are from. Strain labels also indicate which strain component they represent, and the initial coordinates of the node (in brackets) from which the results were obtained. In Figure 6, the labels format is similar to those of Figure 5, but for the force results the direction of the load is also indicated.

For dataset A (tensile tests), the majority of the identified input parameters, from the SHAP analysis, are force values, particularly those obtained for higher values of displacement. For dataset B (cruciform test), the input parameters identified include more

strains values, all of which were obtained from nodes located in the notch area of the cruciform sample, along the edge. However, forces are still the most influential.

From the results of the SHAP analysis, new models were trained, using only those 50 input parameters, and the predictive performance of the new models was evaluated and compared to the original models. These performances are presented in Tables 6 and 7, for datasets A and B, respectively. For reference, the training time for the original models is around 25 seconds, while the training time for the models trained with the inputs identified by SHAP is under 3 seconds.

Fig.5 SHAP values obtained by the 50 most influential input parameters, for dataset A.

Fig.6 SHAP values obtained by the 50 most influential input parameters, for dataset B.

Table 6 – Performance metrics obtained for dataset A when evaluating the original training set and a training set consisting solely of the inputs identified through SHAP analysis.

	RMSRE (%)		R ²		MAE	
	Original	SHAP	Original	SHAP	Original	SHAP
Y_0	0.8083	1.112	0.9996	0.9991	66.9495	82.222
C	0.5189	0.4928	0.9998	0.9997	160.915	165.579
n	1.2058	1.9846	0.9969	0.9918	0.012	0.0212
F	0.7147	11.2443	0.9995	0.9843	0.0758	0.1192
G	0.1448	6.2724	0.9999	0.9499	0.005	0.1162
N	0.4832	1.9566	0.9999	0.9986	0.0847	0.2168

Table 7 – Performance metrics obtained for dataset B when evaluating the original training set and a training set consisting solely of the inputs identified through SHAP analysis.

	RMSRE (%)		R ²		MAE	
	Original	SHAP	Original	SHAP	Original	SHAP
Y_0	1.0634	0.9253	0.9994	0.9996	54.756	40.0452
C	1.6138	1.9781	0.9987	0.998	225.932	409.261
n	3.6923	4.7374	0.9712	0.9532	0.0671	0.0496
F	1.9234	3.8732	0.9982	0.9966	0.0983	0.1129
G	0.6795	2.0363	0.999	0.9899	0.0314	0.1236
N	0.9999	2.691	0.9993	0.9965	0.204	0.4552

The performances obtained by the models trained with only the 50 most influential input parameters are generally worse than the performances obtained by the original models. In regard to the Swift hardening parameters, the differences in performance are relatively small. For the Hill'48 parameters, the differences in performance are more substantial, particularly for the F and G parameters. In order to better understand these differences, Figures 7 and 8 compare the predictions of both models to the real values of the parameters, for datasets A and B respectively.

△ SHAP ◦ Original training set

Fig.7 Comparison between real and predicted values of the constitutive model parameters, for dataset A, considering both the original dataset and the dataset containing the input parameters identified by SHAP: (a) Y_0 ; (b) C ; (c) n ; (d) F ; (e) G ; (f) N

Fig.8 Comparison between real and predicted values of the constitutive model parameters, for dataset B, considering both the original dataset and the dataset containing the input parameters identified by SHAP: (a) Y_0 ; (b) C ; (c) n ; (d) F ; (e) G ; (f) N

For dataset A, it is clear that the predictions for the F and G parameters obtained by the model trained with the inputs identified by SHAP are worse than those obtained by the original model. The predictions for the remaining parameters are comparable. For dataset B, the differences are less noticeable, with predictions errors similar for both models. As such, for dataset B, while the quality of the predictions declined slightly, the use of the model trained with only the most influential input parameters can be recommended. In general, the differences in the performance metrics for this dataset are explained by a few outliers in the testing set.

These results show that the application of SHAP analysis as a dataset reduction methodology is worth considering in some cases. The predictive performances obtained by the models trained with only the most influential input parameters can be comparable to the original models. In those cases, using these new models leads to a more efficient parameter identification process, as less data needs to be collected about a new material in order to obtain the predictions.

9 – Conclusion

In this work, various ML algorithms were applied to the identification of the Swift hardening law and Hill'48 yield criterion parameters. For this purpose, two datasets were created, one containing uniaxial tensile test results and the other containing biaxial tensile test results. Of the ML algorithms tested, GPR achieved the best predictive performances overall, while the SVR algorithm remained competitive. The MLP and the RF algorithms were clearly inferior, with the RF algorithm as the worst. By comparing the performances obtained when training the models with the two datasets used, we can conclude that the dataset containing uniaxial tensile test results allowed for better performances than the dataset containing biaxial tensile test results. When using the GPR algorithm, the average RMSRE values achieved for the two datasets are approximately 0.26% and 0.55%, respectively. Both are considered good performances.

The influence of the dataset size was also analyzed. While the predictive performances are directly correlated to the size of the dataset used to train the models, there is a point after which the increase of dataset size has diminishing returns. For the cases considered in this work, the training sets could be reduced to 1024 materials, from an original size of 4096 materials, before the loss of predictive performance became significant.

Finally, a feature importance evaluation methodology, namely SHAP analysis, was applied to the GPR models, and new models were trained based only on the 50 input parameters

that were identified as most influential. Besides the use of SHAP analysis as an interpretability tool for the original models, the results show that the use of the models created with only the most influential input parameters can be more efficient, in situations where the difference in predictive performance between these models and the original ones is small.

Overall, the results obtained highlight the potential of the proposed methodology, particularly when using the GPR algorithm. The predictive performances achieved, and the quick predictions after model training that are inherent to ML models, show that this methodology is an effective alternative to the classical and inverse constitutive model parameter identification strategies. While these ML algorithms are usually capable of creating good models in the presence of noisy data, this fact should be verified in future research. Also, it would be interesting to test the performance of this methodology with experimental results. This presents some challenges, such as obtaining the force and strain measurements for specific displacements and specimen regions, which may require interpolation, introducing noise in the experimental data.

Finally, the proposed methodology can be applied to more complex constitutive models, which will require the identification of more parameters, and in some cases, the identification of both discrete and continuous parameters [9]. In this context, it may be worth considering the use of more advanced ML algorithms. For example, if the methodology is extended to the identification of kinematic hardening law parameters, the use of algorithms capable of considering the loading history, such as recurrent neural networks, is of interest and worth exploring. Also, for more complex constitutive models, the use of physics-based ML algorithms should be explored. These algorithms can lead to better predictive performances, by imposing restrictions on the algorithms based on well-established physical laws.

Symbology

Symbol	Description
C, ε_0, n	Swift hardening law parameters
E	Young's Modulus
F, G, H, L, M, N	Hill'48 Anisotropy parameters
$f(\mathbf{x})$	GP random variable
f_S	Model trained with features set S
$f_{S \cup \{i\}}$	Model trained with features set S and feature i
$\bar{\mathbf{f}}_*, \mathbf{cov}(\mathbf{f}_*)$	Vector of GPR predictions, covariance of GPR outputs
i, j	Index variables
\mathbf{I}	Identity matrix
\mathbf{K}	Covariance matrix
r_0, r_{45}, r_{90}, r	Anisotropy coefficients
S	Subset of input features from T
T	Set of input features
V	SVM trade-off variable
\mathbf{w}	Normal weight vector
w, d	Weight parameter, bias
\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}_*	Training matrix, testing matrix
$\mathbf{x}^t, \mathbf{x}^p$	Vector of input variables of the training and testing points, respectively
x_S	Values from features in feature set S
$x_{S \cup \{i\}}$	Values from features in feature set S and feature i
y, y^*	Real and predicted response value, respectively
Y	Flow stress
Y_0	Initial yield stress
$y(\mathbf{x})$	Observed outputs for set of inputs \mathbf{x}
z, z'	Output of the current MLP node, output of a node at the previous layer
β_0	Linear function coefficient
γ	SVM threshold parameter
ϵ	Noise variable
$\bar{\varepsilon}^p$	Equivalent plastic strain

$\varepsilon_{xx}, \varepsilon_{yy}, \varepsilon_{xy}$	Components of the Green-Lagrange strain tensor
ξ_i, ξ_i^*	SVM slack variables
$\sigma_{xx}, \sigma_{yy}, \sigma_{zz},$ $\tau_{xy}, \tau_{yz}, \tau_{xz}$	Components of the Cauchy stress tensor
σ_ε^2	Noise variance
\emptyset	Activation function in MLP
Φ_i	Shapley value of input feature i

Acronyms

Symbol	Description
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
FEA	Finite Element Analysis
FEMU	Finite Element Model Updating
GPR	Gaussian Process Regression
MAE	Maximum Absolute Error
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
MSE	Mean Square Error
RF	Random Forest
RMSRE	Root Mean Square Relative Error
SHAP	Shapley Additive Explanations
SVR	Support Vector Regression

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Declaration of competing interests

The authors declare no conflict of interests.

Data and code availability

Data will be made available on request.

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